

Toward Causal Explainability of Neural Networks: Recovering and Validating Global Causal Structure

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Abstract—Neural networks can achieve high predictive accuracy by exploiting statistical dependencies, but this does not show whether they preserve the causal structure of the data-generating process. This paper studies whether global causal structure can be recovered from trained feed-forward multilayer perceptrons. The evaluation uses controlled synthetic structural-equation benchmarks with known graphs and known intervention responses. Feed-forward networks are trained only for supervised prediction. Their internal representations are extracted, aligned to benchmark-referenced variables with a ridge bridge, and passed to the same ordered causal-discovery procedure used on benchmark data. Structural recovery is then complemented by intervention-based validation at the trained model’s input-output boundary. The main evaluation uses two six-variable core benchmarks. Alignment is the dominant factor enabling model-level recovery: median edge F_1 rises from 0.62 to 0.83 in the Linear SEM benchmark and from 0.43 to 0.91 in the nonlinear Current Measurement benchmark. Endpoint-mark recovery remains lower. Benchmark-confirmed output intervention labels are preserved closely at the model boundary, with median precision, recall, specificity, and F_1 equal to 1.00 in both core benchmarks. The recovered partial ancestral graph, however, only partly matches the model’s own intervention responses. These results support model-level causal discovery as a diagnostic tool for feed-forward representations, while showing that a recovered graph is not by itself a complete causal explanation of the trained predictor.

Index Terms—causal explainability, causal discovery, feed-forward neural networks, structural equation models, interventions, representation alignment

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern neural networks can learn accurate predictors, but predictive accuracy alone does not show that a model solves a task for the right reasons. This distinction matters when models are used for scientific interpretation or high-stakes decisions. Common explainability methods make model behaviour more inspectable through feature importance, saliency, and local post-hoc explanations [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. These tools are useful, but they do not establish whether the model has internalized a causal account of the problem it solves.

Causal reasoning asks a different question: what would happen if one part of the system were actively changed and the rest of the mechanism responded accordingly [6, 7]. For explainability, such a view shifts attention from isolated importance scores to variables, pathways, and intervention behaviour. If a causal structure were recoverable from a trained neural network, it could describe which structural relationships of the data-generating process the model has preserved. It

could also expose where the learned predictor follows only predictive shortcuts rather than causal mechanisms [8, 9].

The required causal objects can be stated compactly. A structural equation model (SEM) assigns each variable from its direct causes and an exogenous disturbance; its graph is a directed acyclic graph (DAG) when the assignments are acyclic. An intervention $do(X_i = x)$ replaces the structural assignment for X_i by a fixed value and lets the remaining equations respond. From observational data, discovery usually returns an equivalence-class summary rather than a unique DAG; here this summary is a partial ancestral graph (PAG), whose adjacencies and endpoint marks must be interpreted as supported causal claims rather than as a complete mechanism [10].

Existing causal-explainability work gives reasons for optimism but leaves an architectural and methodological gap. Causal abstraction aligns neural representations with hypothesized high-level causal variables and tests them through interventions [11]. Interchange-intervention training can further induce neural models to match target causal behaviour [12]. Attention-based approaches recover causal structures from Transformer representations in instance- or sequence-level settings [13, 14]. These settings either require a pre-specified high-level causal model, rely on attention mechanisms, or produce local structures for individual inputs. It remains less clear whether a single global causal structure can be recovered from non-attention feed-forward representations after ordinary supervised training.

The recovery target is deliberately modest. Observational causal discovery usually cannot identify one unique fully oriented DAG, because multiple DAGs can imply the same conditional-independence pattern [7]. The recovered object is therefore a PAG, which summarizes adjacencies and endpoint marks supported by the available information [10]. In this paper, model-derived variables denote quantities extracted from the trained network, especially hidden activations and pre-activations represented as tabular features. The question is not whether these coordinates are causal variables by themselves, but whether they retain enough information to recover a benchmark-comparable global graph after alignment.

This paper addresses that question in a controlled setting. Synthetic structural equation models (SEMs) provide benchmark data, ground-truth directed acyclic graphs (DAGs), and intervention responses. Feed-forward multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) are trained only for prediction. Their model-

derived variables are then extracted, aligned, and analysed with causal discovery. The same discovery procedure is also applied directly to benchmark samples, which gives a data-level reference for interpreting model-level recovery.

The paper makes three contributions. First, it gives an end-to-end protocol for comparing data-level and model-level causal recovery under known ground truth. Second, it shows that observable-state alignment is essential for recovering edge-level structure from feed-forward representations. Third, it separates structural recovery from behavioural validation by comparing recovered PAGs, model responses under simulated interventions, and calibrated effect magnitudes. The evaluation is organized around five questions: structural recovery from model-derived variables, agreement between model-level PAG total-effect claims and model intervention responses, preservation of benchmark-confirmed output intervention labels, preservation of standardized intervention-effect magnitudes, and robustness across architectures, folds, discovery settings, and benchmark families. This structure keeps graph recovery, graph-to-behaviour consistency, and effect-size calibration distinct rather than treating a single structural score as sufficient evidence.

II. METHODS

A. Research Design and Benchmarks

The study uses controlled synthetic SEMs rather than real-world observational data. This choice is deliberate: the goal is not to infer an unknown real-world mechanism, but to test what remains recoverable after a known causal system has been learned by a feed-forward neural network. All benchmark variables are fully observed. Each variable is either an input to the predictive model or one of its prediction targets. This makes the evaluation diagnostically clean, but it also makes the setting more favourable than applications with latent variables or unmeasured confounding.

This design also separates benchmark truth from the learned predictor. The total number of benchmark variables equals the number of observed inputs plus predicted outputs, so every benchmark node remains visible somewhere at the supervised model interface. Disagreements between recovered and true structure can therefore be localized without first solving a missing-variable problem. The price of this control is limited external validity: the results do not establish behaviour for real-world data, indirect measurements, latent confounding, or larger causal systems.

The main evaluation uses two core six-variable benchmarks. The Linear SEM benchmark is a random connected acyclic linear system with abstract variables X_0, \dots, X_5 . The variables are ordered, arrows are allowed only from earlier to later variables, and the predictive split is (X_0, X_1, X_2) as inputs and (X_3, X_4, X_5) as targets. For each admissible ordered pair $i < j$, an edge is sampled with probability $p = 2/5 = 0.4$, corresponding to target expected neighbourhood size two. Disconnected candidates are rejected, and the accepted six-node instance must also satisfy a validity rule: every predicted target has at least one input ancestor and at least one input

non-ancestor. Present edges receive fixed random signed coefficients with absolute values in $[0.5, 2.0]$, and observations follow

$$X_j = \varepsilon_j + \sum_{i \in \text{Pa}(j)} w_{ij} X_i, \quad \varepsilon_j \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1).$$

Here, $\text{Pa}(j)$ denotes the parent set of X_j in the sampled DAG, w_{ij} is the fixed coefficient on edge $i \rightarrow j$, and ε_j is an independent exogenous noise term. The graph construction follows the order-constrained connected-graph logic used in Intel Labs' causality-lab implementation [15].

The Current Measurement benchmark is a fixed nonlinear six-variable SEM with interpreted variables V, R, G, I, S , and O , denoting voltage, resistance, gain, current, sensor reading, and output. The predictive split is (V, R, G) as inputs and (I, S, O) as targets. Its structural equations are

$$\begin{aligned} V &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1), & R &\sim \mathcal{U}(1, 10), & G &\sim \mathcal{U}(0.5, 2.0), \\ I &= \frac{V}{R + 10^{-8}}, & S &= I + \varepsilon_S, & O &= GS + \varepsilon_O, \end{aligned}$$

with $\varepsilon_S \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1^2)$ and $\varepsilon_O = 0$. The small denominator constant is a numerical safeguard. The graph is therefore fixed by the equations: voltage and resistance determine current, current determines sensor reading, and gain scales the sensor reading into output.

Eight additional templated SEM families are used as robustness checks. They include chain, fork-collider, and layered-sparse topologies with linear and nonlinear mechanisms; the layered-sparse linear topology is additionally evaluated with two non-Gaussian noise variants. In these families, the final three variables are prediction targets and all earlier variables are inputs. Chain graphs concentrate effects along one mediated path, fork-collider graphs combine shared-cause and common-effect motifs, and layered-sparse graphs separate upstream, intermediate, and output stages while remaining sparse as node count grows. The linear variants use fixed signed edge weights and additive disturbances drawn from Gaussian, Laplace, or Student- t_3 distributions. The nonlinear variants retain the seeded graph but transform parent values with a deterministic mix of identity, mildly quadratic, and tanh edge-level functions before summation. Together with the two core benchmarks, these variants form the ten benchmark families used for the paper's robustness summaries.

B. Pipeline

Fig. 1 summarizes the nine-step workflow. Each experiment uses five folds. A fold is not a cross-validation slice of one empirical dataset. Rather, each fold is a fresh stochastic draw from the same fixed benchmark SEM. The graph, parameters, sample size, and simulation protocol remain fixed; only the stochastic realizations are resampled. A fold contains 12,000 observations: 10,000 form the main supervised-learning pool and 2,000 form the extraction pool. The main pool is split deterministically into 8,000 training, 1,000 validation, and 1,000 test observations. The extraction pool is split into 1,000 bridge-estimation rows and 1,000 bridge-application rows.

Fig. 1. Nine-step evaluation pipeline. Synthetic SEMs define benchmark data, ground-truth graphs, and intervention responses. Feed-forward MLPs are trained on the predictive task, their representations are extracted and aligned, and causal discovery is applied both to benchmark data and to model-derived variables.

TABLE I
FEED-FORWARD MODEL ARCHITECTURES

Model	Hidden structure	Main components	Params.
Shallow	32–32	ReLU	1,283
Deep	64–64–64–64	GELU, dropout 0.1	12,931
Bottleneck	128–16–128	SiLU bottleneck	5,139
Gated	64–64–64–64	SiLU value path, sigmoid gates, dropout 0.1	25,667
Residual	128 units, 3 blocks	GELU residual blocks	99,971
Tabular	256–128–64	SiLU, batch normalization, dropout 0.1	43,267

Training-set statistics are used to standardize predictors and targets; validation, test, and extraction data reuse those same statistics.

Six feed-forward MLP families are evaluated: Shallow, Deep, Bottleneck, Gated, Residual, and Tabular variants. All are ordinary supervised regressors implemented in PyTorch [16]. They share the same benchmark-adapted input-output interface and terminate in a linear projection to the target variables. Table I gives the implemented core-benchmark architectures.

All six models remain within the ordinary feed-forward setting. They vary capacity, information flow, bottlenecking, gating, skip connections, and tabular regularization, but they do not receive causal objectives or causal architectural constraints. Training uses mean squared error loss and AdamW [17]. The profiles are fixed rather than tuned: Shallow models use 40 maximum epochs and learning rate 10^{-3} ; Deep, Bottleneck, Gated, and Tabular models use 60 maximum epochs and learning rate 8×10^{-4} ; Residual models use 80 maximum epochs and learning rate 6×10^{-4} . Batch size is 512, validation loss alone controls early stopping and checkpoint selection, and the

best-validation checkpoint is restored for later extraction. The test split is used only for held-out predictive diagnostics, not for selecting the downstream causal analysis.

C. Representation Extraction and Alignment

After training, the retained checkpoint is used to extract model-derived variables on held-out extraction rows. Extraction uses the same trained model and training-split normalization statistics as prediction, but no extraction rows are used for model fitting or checkpoint selection. A shared extraction interface built around PyTorch modules and forward hooks records tabular rows from different architectures in a consistent format. The main internal readouts are hidden activations and pre-activations. Activation extraction stores nonlinear-module outputs, while pre-activation extraction records affine-layer outputs before later nonlinear transformations. Additional Shallow MLP checks compare these readouts with observable input-output and learned-weight baselines (Appendix A).

Raw hidden coordinates are not directly comparable with benchmark variables, so the model-level branch uses a supervised alignment step. The bridge maps selected internal representation columns into a benchmark-referenced target space while keeping rows fixed.

Two alignment targets are used. SEM-target alignment maps internal representations to the full benchmark SEM state. It is an oracle comparator because it uses ground-truth benchmark variables as the target. Observable-state alignment maps internal representations to $[\mathbf{x}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}]$, the raw benchmark inputs concatenated with the model’s raw predictions for the same sample. This is the main realistic condition because it uses variables visible at the trained model interface.

The bridge is a ridge-regularized multi-output linear map [18]. It is fitted only on the 1,000 bridge-estimation rows and applied unchanged to the separate 1,000 bridge-application rows. Input/output columns are removed from the representation-side input before bridge fitting, so the bridge uses internal model coordinates rather than trivially copying observed variables. Let \mathcal{E} and \mathcal{A} denote the bridge-estimation and bridge-application row sets. With estimation-standardized internal coordinates $\bar{\mathbf{z}}_{\text{est}}^{(i)}$ and target coordinates $\bar{\mathbf{t}}^{(i)}$, the fitted bridge is

$$(\hat{W}, \hat{\mathbf{b}}) = \arg \min_{W, \mathbf{b}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{E}} \left\| \bar{\mathbf{t}}^{(i)} - \left(W \bar{\mathbf{z}}_{\text{est}}^{(i)} + \mathbf{b} \right) \right\|_2^2 + \lambda \|W\|_F^2,$$

with $\lambda = 10^{-3}$. For each $j \in \mathcal{A}$, the same representation columns are standardized with estimation-side statistics and mapped by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{t}}^{(j)} = \left(\hat{W} \bar{\mathbf{z}}_{\text{app}}^{(j)} + \hat{\mathbf{b}} \right) \odot \sigma_t + \mu_t,$$

where μ_t and σ_t are target means and standard deviations from the estimation rows. No systematic sensitivity analysis over λ is performed. The aligned output is therefore a target-space proxy predicted from internal model coordinates, not a direct measurement of a causal variable.

The no-alignment condition applies causal discovery directly to raw model-derived coordinates from the bridge-application split. It is therefore an ablation for what is readable from model space without supervised translation, not a benchmark-space graph in the same sense as the aligned conditions.

D. Causal Discovery and Structural Evaluation

Causal discovery is applied to two branches. The data-level branch receives benchmark observations. The model-level branch receives raw or aligned model-derived variables. Both branches use the same downstream configuration within each benchmark. The output is a PAG rather than a fully oriented DAG, because observational conditional-independence information usually identifies equivalence classes rather than one unique graph [10, 7].

The discovery algorithm is ordered iterative causal discovery (ICD) [19]. It uses the known benchmark variable order as background knowledge. This is a semi-oracle assumption: it does not reveal the graph, but it rules out directions inconsistent with the benchmark construction. The assumption is useful for isolating representation effects, but it would not automatically hold in real applications. Linear Gaussian settings use partial-correlation tests; nonlinear continuous settings use kernel-based conditional-independence tests [20, 21]. The default significance threshold is 0.01. The default discovery sample budget is 150 rows for both data-level and model-level runs, even though larger extraction pools are available for robustness checks.

These PAGs are interpreted as conditional-independence summaries, not as fully identified causal DAGs. The discovery procedure removes adjacencies when the CI tests support independence between two variables given a tested conditioning set; remaining edges are dependencies that survived those tests, not direct evidence of a particular SEM equation. Endpoint marks encode orientation information at the equivalence-class level: tails and arrowheads record supported ancestral constraints, while circle endpoints remain unresolved. The method assumes that statistical independences are informative about graph separation under the benchmark regime; poor CI test behaviour can therefore produce graph error even before model representations are considered [22]. A missing PAG edge is evidence against a supported direct adjacency claim in the recovered equivalence-class summary, but it does not rule out every possible indirect total effect. Conversely, a compatible directed path is a graph-side claim that still needs behavioural validation against model responses.

Structural evaluation compares recovered PAGs with the benchmark DAG. The main metrics are edge F_1 , endpoint-mark F_1 , strict structural Hamming distance (SHD), and partial SHD. Edge F_1 measures adjacency recovery. Endpoint-mark F_1 measures recovery of PAG endpoint marks, not complete DAG orientation. Strict SHD penalizes unresolved endpoints more strongly than partial SHD.

E. Intervention-Based Evaluation

Structural agreement does not prove behavioural fidelity. Intervention evaluation therefore asks whether graph claims and model responses agree under simulated benchmark interventions. For each treatment variable, low and high intervention values are chosen as the 0.2 and 0.8 quantiles of its fold-specific observational distribution. For each regime, 2,000 new samples are generated from the manipulated SEM. The intervention replaces the equation for the treatment variable with a constant assignment; all other variables are generated from the SEM with fresh disturbances. For treatment i and outcome j , the benchmark-side contrast is

$$\widehat{\text{ATE}}_{ij}^{\text{bench}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{r=1}^n X_{j,\text{high}}^{(r)} - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{r=1}^n X_{j,\text{low}}^{(r)}, \quad n = 2,000.$$

The trained predictor is evaluated on the observed input slice of these interventional samples. The benchmark intervention does not manually edit one row and keep all other columns fixed. It regenerates a complete sample from the manipulated SEM, so downstream benchmark mechanisms and fresh disturbances can respond to the treatment assignment. Because the model maps only from inputs \mathbf{x} to outputs $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, the main model-side intervention summaries are restricted to ordered input-output pairs. In the two core benchmarks this gives $3 \times 3 = 9$ pairs per fold-model block.

The 0.2–0.8 contrast is a moderate within-distribution intervention. It creates a visible shift while avoiding tail interventions where nonlinear mechanisms or rare-noise realizations could dominate the comparison. The same contrast is reused for all outcomes of a treatment within a fold. No sensitivity analysis over alternative intervention strengths is performed, so intervention results should be read relative to this fixed contrast.

The benchmark-side and model-side effects use the same confirmed-effect rule. First, the low-high average treatment effect (ATE) must pass an unstandardized magnitude threshold $\tau = 0.05$. Second, a two-sample Kolmogorov–Smirnov test must indicate a distributional difference at $\alpha = 0.05$ [23]. A confirmed effect is present only when both checks pass:

$$e_{ij}^{\text{confirmed}} = \mathbb{I}\left(\left|\widehat{\text{ATE}}_{ij}\right| \geq \tau\right) \mathbb{I}(p_{ij}^{\text{KS}} < \alpha).$$

Continuous calibration compares standardized ATE magnitudes,

$$\widehat{\text{ATE}}_{ij}^{\text{std}} = \widehat{\text{ATE}}_{ij} / \text{sd}_{\text{obs}}(X_j),$$

where the denominator is the observational standard deviation of the benchmark outcome variable in the current fold. DoWhy estimates provide a benchmark-aware observational reference using the true benchmark DAG and valid adjustment sets [24]. The DoWhy estimate is fitted on non-interventional benchmark samples with the same low-versus-high contrast and enters the analysis as a descriptive calibration comparator, not as a second intervention truth.

Graph-based intervention claims are derived separately from the recovered model-level PAG. A direct-effect claim requires

TABLE II
STRUCTURAL RECOVERY SUMMARY

Dataset	Branch	Edge F_1	End. F_1	Str. SHD	Part. SHD
Linear	Data	0.83	0.50	6	4
	No align.	0.62	0.35	10	8
	Obs. align.	0.83	0.44	8	5
Current	Data	0.89	0.67	3	1
	No align.	0.43	0.23	10	9
	Obs. align.	0.91	0.55	5	2

a forward edge compatible with causal direction from treatment to outcome. The intervention consistency analysis uses the broader total-effect claim: whether the PAG allows the treatment to be a possible ancestor of the outcome. These graph-side claims are binary and have no effect magnitude. They are therefore compared with confirmed model-response labels, while continuous calibration is restricted to ATE estimates.

III. RESULTS

A. Data-Level Reference

Data-level discovery establishes the benchmark-side recovery difficulty before any predictive model is involved. Table II shows that discovery from benchmark samples is strong but not perfect. In the Linear SEM benchmark, median data-level edge F_1 is 0.83 and endpoint-mark F_1 is 0.50. Current Measurement has higher central data-level scores under the default configuration, with median edge $F_1 = 0.89$ and endpoint-mark $F_1 = 0.67$. These values form the reference for interpreting the model-level branch. A model-level error should not be attributed to the neural network when the same discovery procedure already has residual data-level error.

B. Predictive Sanity Check

The trained MLPs also pass predictive diagnostics before their representations are interpreted causally. Fold-aggregated training and validation trajectories do not indicate meaningful overfitting. Held-out test losses remain close to the best validation losses in the Linear SEM runs and are lower than the corresponding validation losses in the Current Measurement runs. In the Linear SEM benchmark, the mean test-minus-best-validation loss gap is small across architectures, ranging from about 0.0002 to 0.0018. In Current Measurement, the same gap is negative for all retained architectures, ranging from about -0.0034 to -0.0052 . The structural and intervention results are therefore not explained by an obvious optimization failure or gross train-test mismatch. Prediction quality is not the evaluation target, but this check makes the trained models suitable objects for the later causal diagnostics.

C. Alignment Enables Model-Level Recovery

Fig. 2 shows that alignment is the dominant factor for model-level structural recovery. Without alignment, causal connections are not directly readable from raw model-derived variables. In the Linear SEM benchmark, observable-state alignment raises median edge F_1 from 0.62 to 0.83, raises

Fig. 2. Model-level structural recovery by alignment target, scored against benchmark ground truth. Observable-state alignment substantially improves edge recovery in both core benchmarks, while endpoint-mark recovery remains lower. SEM-target alignment is an oracle comparator.

endpoint-mark F_1 from 0.35 to 0.44, and reduces median strict and partial SHD from 10 to 8 and from 8 to 5. In Current Measurement, the same change raises median edge F_1 from 0.43 to 0.91 and endpoint-mark F_1 from 0.23 to 0.55, while reducing strict and partial SHD from 10 to 5 and from 9 to 2.

The improvement is statistically robust in the full fold-architecture analysis. Friedman omnibus tests confirm alignment effects in all dataset-metric blocks after Benjamini-Hochberg correction ($q \leq 0.011$), and paired Wilcoxon contrasts show observable-state alignment improving all four metrics over no alignment in both benchmarks ($q \leq 0.0012$). SEM-target alignment is strongest for Current Measurement, where it reaches median edge $F_1 = 1.00$, endpoint-mark $F_1 = 0.70$, strict SHD = 3, and partial SHD = 0. It is not uniformly superior in the Linear SEM benchmark, where observable-state alignment remains stronger for the two F_1 metrics. The oracle target therefore helps interpret what could be recovered under privileged information, but it is not the main deployable condition.

D. Model-Level Recovery Relative to Data-Level Recovery

The matched data-model comparison separates discovery difficulty from additional model-side loss. Fig. 3 shows paired data- and model-level scores together with matched model-minus-data deltas across the two core benchmarks and six retained MLP architectures. Without alignment, the model branch loses substantial recoverable structure: the median model-minus-data delta is -0.39 for edge F_1 and -0.36 for endpoint-mark F_1 . Observable-state alignment reduces the median edge- F_1 delta to -0.03 , and this delta is no longer significant after correction ($q = 0.170$). Endpoint-mark recovery remains below the data-level reference, with median

Fig. 3. Matched data- and model-level recovery against benchmark ground truth. Alignment moves model-level edge recovery close to the matched data-level reference, while endpoint-mark recovery remains weaker.

delta -0.07 and $q < 0.001$. Thus, edge presence is easier to preserve and recover than endpoint information.

Extraction-mode checks show little practical separation between activations and pre-activations once observable-state alignment is used. In the Linear SEM benchmark, median edge F_1 differs by at most 0.01 between these readouts. In Current Measurement, both reach median edge $F_1 = 0.91$. Endpoint-mark medians are also identical within each benchmark. Corrected paired contrasts are not significant ($q \geq 0.934$). The appendix extends this comparison with observable input-output and learned-weight baselines for the Shallow MLP. In this feed-forward setting, the alignment target and observable variable space matter more than choosing between retained hidden-state readouts.

E. Input-Output Intervention Effects Are Preserved

The next analysis compares benchmark-confirmed output effects with the trained model’s output responses under the same simulated interventions. For each fold and architecture, the analysis considers the nine ordered input-output pairs.

Fig. 4 and Table III show strong preservation at this input-output boundary. Median precision, recall, specificity, and F_1 are all 1.00 in both benchmarks. In the median Linear SEM block, the benchmark and model both confirm five of nine output effects. In Current Measurement, both confirm three of nine. Individual fold-architecture cells can deviate from perfect agreement, so this is not exact equality for every trained model. At the aggregate level, however, ordinary supervised training

Fig. 4. Benchmark-to-model detection of output intervention effects. Median precision, recall, specificity, and F_1 are 1.00 in both core benchmarks for the corrected input-output interface comparison.

TABLE III
INTERVENTION FIDELITY SUMMARY

Dataset	Effects	Det. F_1	PAG agr.	Overclaim	Std. MAE
Linear	5/9	1.00	0.78	0.00	0.038
Current	3/9	1.00	0.56	0.44	0.017

does not erase the tested external intervention-response pattern.

F. Recovered PAGs Only Partly Match Model Responses

The recovered model-level PAG is a candidate explanation of model behaviour. It should therefore be checked against the trained model’s own intervention responses. Fig. 5 and Table III report this diagnostic by comparing PAG-implied total-effect claims with model-confirmed output-response labels for the same input-output pairs.

The result is benchmark-dependent. Linear SEM reaches median agreement 0.78 and median $F_1 = 0.75$. Current Measurement reaches median agreement 0.56 and median $F_1 = 0.60$. The error modes differ: Linear SEM mainly misses some confirmed model effects, while Current Measurement mainly overclaims effects that the model does not confirm. This is the key cautionary result. A model-level PAG can recover useful structure and still be an imperfect behavioural explanation of the predictor.

High PAG-to-model agreement would also not prove benchmark causal correctness. This diagnostic compares the graph-side total-effect claim with the trained model’s own output-response label. It is therefore an internal coherence check for the explanation layer, not a second ground-truth structural test.

PAG-to-Model Consistency with Output Intervention Responses

Fig. 5. PAG-to-model consistency for output intervention responses. Agreement, miss rate, overclaim rate, and model-confirmed effect rate compare each model-level PAG total-effect claim with the same model’s confirmed response label.

Fig. 6. Continuous intervention-effect calibration error for benchmark-confirmed output effects. Model-derived estimates remain close to benchmark intervention magnitudes at the input-output boundary, with a small calibration loss relative to the DoWhy reference.

G. Effect Magnitudes Remain Closely Calibrated

Finally, the analysis compares standardized intervention-effect magnitudes for benchmark-confirmed output effects. Fig. 6 summarizes standardized mean absolute error (MAE) for the benchmark-aware DoWhy reference and the model-derived estimates. The DoWhy reference is closely calibrated, with pooled standardized MAE 0.017. Model-derived estimates are also close, although slightly less accurate overall: pooled standardized MAE is 0.030.

By dataset, model-side standardized MAE is 0.038 for Linear SEM and 0.017 for Current Measurement. The corresponding DoWhy values are 0.016 and 0.019. The pooled model-side correlation with benchmark standardized ATEs is near one, and the model-minus-DoWhy MAE gap is +0.012. These

calibration summaries are descriptive rather than formal line-versus-identity tests. They apply only to benchmark-confirmed input-output effects, not to hidden-unit interventions or effects among predicted target variables.

H. Robustness Checks

Architecture-level checks show that the main structural pattern is not tied to one feed-forward architecture. Under observable-state alignment, architecture-level median edge F_1 ranges from 0.71 to 0.92 in Linear SEM and from 0.80 to 1.00 in Current Measurement. Endpoint-mark F_1 remains lower, ranging from 0.40 to 0.47 and from 0.50 to 0.70, respectively. Corrected Friedman tests do not support a robust architecture effect for edge or endpoint recovery ($q = 0.464$ across the reported structural comparisons), and paired Wilcoxon contrasts against the Shallow MLP do not isolate a reliably different architecture after correction.

The intervention-side architecture check is similarly stable. Median output F_1 ranges from 0.91 to 1.00 in Linear SEM and is 1.00 for all retained architectures in Current Measurement. Median standardized MAE remains between 0.017 and 0.039 in Linear SEM and between 0.009 and 0.036 in Current Measurement. Corrected architecture tests do not show robust intervention-side differences.

Discovery-configuration and benchmark-expansion checks qualify the conclusions. Conditional-independence threshold choice and mismatched CI tests do not dominate the structural conclusion: corrected threshold trend tests have $q \geq 0.416$, and mismatched-CI Wilcoxon checks remain at $q \geq 0.300$. Node-count sweeps do not show a corrected model-minus-data trend ($q \geq 0.126$). Sample size is the main caveat. In Current Measurement, data-truth edge F_1 increases with larger discovery samples ($\rho = 0.657, q < 0.001$), while model-truth edge F_1 decreases ($\rho = -0.505, q < 0.001$). Larger discovery samples can therefore make the data-level reference clearer while exposing model-level distortions more sharply. Across the ten benchmark families, model-PAG consistency remains dataset-dependent, with median agreement from 0.33 to 0.78. The dominant error mode also changes: Current Measurement mainly overclaims, whereas several expanded SEM families have little median overclaiming but miss about 0.56–0.67 of model-confirmed effects. Appendix C shows this expanded consistency check. This is why PAG consistency is reported as a diagnostic, not as a uniform behavioural guarantee.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Interpretation

The results support a limited but useful form of causal recoverability. Feed-forward neural networks can preserve information from which parts of a known causal structure remain recoverable. However, this information is not directly available in raw hidden coordinates. It becomes useful only after an alignment bridge maps model-derived representations into a benchmark-comparable space.

The distinction between structural recovery and behavioural validation is central. If only edge-level graph scores were considered, observable-state alignment would make the method look close to the data-level reference. If only input-output intervention detection were considered, the median F_1 of 1.00 would suggest strong preservation of intervention behaviour. The combined view is more specific: the predictor can behave faithfully at its external boundary while the recovered PAG remains an incomplete and sometimes overclaiming explanation of that behaviour.

This result is consistent with the broader causal-inference view that explanation requires mechanisms and interventions rather than association alone [6, 7]. It also fits the caution that neural networks can exploit predictive shortcuts without necessarily representing the full data-generating process [8, 9]. Compared with attention-based causal explanation work, the present setting shows that causal traces are not limited to Transformer attention. Compared with causal-abstraction methods, it also shows why alignment must be paired with behavioural tests rather than treated as sufficient evidence of causal implementation.

The comparison with causal abstraction is especially important. Causal-abstraction workflows ask whether internal neural states can be aligned with a hypothesized high-level causal model and then tested through interchange interventions [11]. Interchange-intervention training goes further by explicitly optimizing for such counterfactual agreement [12]. The present MLPs are weaker but more diagnostic in a different sense: they receive no causal objective and no pre-specified high-level causal graph. The recovered structure is discovered after ordinary supervised training. The positive result is that aligned edge-level structure can approach the data-level reference; the negative result is that endpoint recovery and PAG-to-model response consistency still lag. This makes the method a diagnostic for recoverable causal traces, not a demonstration that the network implements the benchmark SEM.

The comparison with attention-based work is different. Transformer studies can use attention-derived signals to build sequence- or instance-level causal explanations [13, 14]. The present study instead asks for one global graph from non-attention feed-forward representations. Its success therefore does not depend on attention weights, but its scope is also narrower: the benchmarks are small, fully observed, and synthetic. The central implication is methodological rather than architectural. A recovered graph should be handled as a set of candidate causal claims, then tested against intervention responses from the trained model before being presented as an explanation.

B. Limitations

Several limitations narrow the claim. First, the benchmarks are synthetic, small, and fully observed. This gives clean ground truth but does not establish behaviour under latent confounding, noisy measurement, larger graphs, real deployment data, or changing environments.

Second, the discovery procedure uses known benchmark variable order as semi-oracle background knowledge. This focuses the study on representation effects, but it makes the discovery setting more favourable than many real applications.

Third, the predictive models are ordinary supervised MLPs. Remaining failures may arise from training, representation extraction, alignment, discovery, or their interaction. The present evaluation can compare these branches descriptively, but it does not identify a unique internal cause for every mismatch.

Fourth, the intervention analysis is limited to observed inputs and predicted outputs. It does not intervene on hidden units, predicted target variables, or mechanisms outside the supervised model interface.

Finally, aligned coordinates should not be overinterpreted as recovered causal variables. The alignment bridge is a predictive translation from internal coordinates to a target space. Aligned-proxy diagnostics (Appendix B) show that observable-state proxies can be weaker than SEM-target proxies in some settings. This reinforces the main conclusion: aligned model-level graphs should be treated as candidate explanations requiring behavioural validation, not as direct causal identifications.

C. Future Work

A natural next step is to turn the recovered PAG into an explicitly checked explanation. The PAG should first be treated as a set of candidate total-effect claims. Each claim should then be tested against held-out model interventions. Claims with corresponding detectable model responses would be retained; unsupported claims would be removed or marked uncertain. The intervention pairs used to filter claims should be separated from the pairs used to evaluate the final explanation, so that graph refinement and validation remain distinct.

The same protocol should then be tested on models with explicit causal objectives. Interchange-intervention training and related causal-abstraction methods are natural candidates [11, 12]. The central question is whether such models improve model-response agreement and effect-magnitude calibration, or whether they mainly improve structural graph scores.

V. CONCLUSION

Feed-forward neural representations can retain recoverable traces of global causal structure after suitable alignment, and trained predictors can preserve external input-output intervention effects in small controlled SEM benchmarks. The recovered graph is therefore useful as a diagnostic summary, but not as a standalone causal explanation. Model-level causal discovery becomes credible only when structural recovery is checked against how the trained model actually behaves under interventions.

APPENDIX A ADDITIONAL EXTRACTION-MODE CHECKS

The main extraction-mode comparison uses hidden activations and pre-activations because both are sample-wise internal readouts available across the retained feed-forward

Additional Extraction Modes Under Observable-State Alignment

Fig. 7. Additional extraction-mode comparison for observable-state-aligned Shallow MLP runs. Panels pair absolute model-level PAG scores against the ground-truth DAG with matched model-minus-data differences, $\Delta = \text{model} - \text{data}$, for edge F_1 and endpoint-mark F_1 across Linear SEM and Current Measurement. Points show matched fold observations.

architectures. A supplementary Shallow MLP check compares these readouts with two simpler baselines under observable-state alignment: an input-output table containing standardized inputs and model outputs, and a learned-weight representation that repeats the trained parameter vector for compatibility with the row-wise discovery pipeline. The weight mode is therefore exploratory, because it does not provide genuine sample-wise variation.

Fig. 7 shows that the input-output baseline closely follows the hidden-state readouts in this slice. The repeated-weight baseline is lower, with median edge F_1 of 0.47 and 0.44 and endpoint-mark F_1 of 0.24 and 0.25 for Linear SEM and Current Measurement, respectively. In the same appendix slice, activation extraction reaches median edge F_1 of 0.83 in both benchmarks and endpoint-mark F_1 of 0.46 and 0.50. Corrected contrasts against activations are not significant ($q_{\text{BH}} = 0.188$ for weights, $q_{\text{BH}} = 1.000$ otherwise), so these five-fold checks are descriptive support rather than a primary claim.

APPENDIX B

ALIGNED PROXY INTERVENTION DIAGNOSTICS

The main intervention analysis tests externally settable benchmark inputs and model-output responses. The aligned-proxy diagnostic in Fig. 8 asks a narrower question: whether benchmark-aware DoWhy estimates computed on aligned proxy variables still match benchmark interventional ATE magnitudes. This isolates the alignment step, but it is not a causal validation of the aligned coordinates, because the proxy variables cannot be intervened on directly.

The diagnostic is mixed. For Linear SEM, SEM-target alignment is closer to the benchmark intervention effects than

Aligned Proxy Variables Compared with SEM Intervention Effects

Fig. 8. Diagnostic comparison of DoWhy estimates from aligned proxy variables with benchmark SEM intervention effects. Panels show benchmark interventional ATEs against aligned-space DoWhy estimates for Linear SEM and Current Measurement under observable-state and SEM-target alignment. Point colour marks whether the benchmark SEM confirms an intervention effect.

observable-state alignment, with MAE 0.096 instead of 0.372 and correlation $r = 0.97$ instead of 0.66. Current Measurement changes little across the two alignment targets, with MAE about 0.022 and $r = 0.97$. Sign agreement remains low, between 0.24 and 0.29. The plot should therefore be read as a rough scale-and-order check, not as evidence for individual aligned-coordinate effects.

APPENDIX C

EXPANDED MODEL-PAG CONSISTENCY

Fig. 9 extends the model-PAG behavioural consistency check from the two core benchmarks to ten benchmark families. This benchmark-expansion view is a descriptive generalization check and should be read as dataset-level context for the core intervention results, not as evidence that one agreement level holds across all synthetic benchmark families.

Across the ten benchmark families, median agreement ranges from 0.33 in several expanded SEM families to 0.78 in Linear SEM. Current Measurement has median agreement 0.56, no median PAG misses, and a high median PAG overclaim rate of 0.44, matching the overclaim pattern reported in the main results. The expanded SEM families show a different limitation: most have median overclaim rates of 0.00, but median miss rates around 0.56–0.67. Median F_1 ranges from 0.50 in several expanded families to 0.80 in Chain Linear SEM and Linear SEM. The expanded benchmarks therefore support the same caution as the core analysis: model-PAG agreement with the model’s own intervention responses is not stable across benchmark families, and the dominant error mode depends on the dataset.

Fig. 9. Model-level PAG behavioural consistency for output interventions across expanded benchmark families under observable-state alignment. Panels report agreement rate, PAG miss rate, PAG overclaim rate, and model-confirmed effect rate by comparing whether the PAG predicts a total effect with the same model’s confirmed response label. Each point summarizes one fold-level Shallow MLP observation over $n = 9$ ordered treatment-output pairs. Dataset codes denote the ten benchmark families listed on the x-axis.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS AND THESIS ORIGIN

Hannes Steiner conducted the research, including study conception, data collection, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. This paper is derived from his master’s thesis at the UAS Technikum Wien, which is available from the university library. Lars Mehnen supervised the research process on a regular basis, provided conceptual guidance, critically reviewed the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The implementation and reproducibility material are available in the project repository: <https://github.com/SteinerHannes/NeuralCausalDiscovery.git>. The analyses in this paper use synthetic benchmark data and reporting outputs produced by that pipeline.

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